

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF A CONVENTIONAL AND AN ALTERNATIVE SINGLE-FAMILY HOUSE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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Abstract. The construction sector is responsible for a significant proportion of global carbon emissions, with environmental performance increasingly recognized as a critical factor in the sustainable design of buildings. This study compares the environmental impact of two single-family houses built in south-east Europe using life cycle assessment. A conventional masonry house was built using bricks and concrete. An alternative house was built using natural and locally sourced materials. The alternative house features timber construction and hemp-based insulation and is an example of an environmentally friendly approach that emphasizes material efficiency and reduced environmental impact. The conventional house, on the other hand, reflects standard practices that rely on energy-intensive material production processes. This study focuses on global warming potential (GWP), from raw material extraction to end-of-life. The results show that the alternative house achieves a significantly better environmental balance due to its renewable materials and resource efficiency, while the conventional house generates higher emissions due to its energy-intensive material production. These results highlight the benefits of green materials and sustainable practices in reducing the environmental footprint of housing construction.

Keywords: Life Cycle Assessment, Environmental impact, Natural materials, Global Warming Potential, End of Life.

1 Introduction

The construction sector is one of the biggest emitters of greenhouse gasses worldwide. According to the Global Status Report 2024-2025 for Buildings and Construction by the United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) and the Global Alliance for Buildings and Construction (GlobalABC), the building and construction sector contributes significantly to global CO₂ emissions, with the building sector alone responsible for 34% of these emissions. In addition, materials such as cement and steel are responsible for 18% of total CO₂ emissions from the construction sector [1]. A significant portion of these emissions come from the embodied carbon associated with materials and construction processes. As a result, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has become an indispensable tool for assessing the environmental performance of buildings at all life cycle stages, from raw material extraction to end-of-life [2].

Recent studies emphasize the urgent need to replace traditional, carbon-intensive materials, such as concrete and brick, with renewable and locally produced alternatives. Bio-based materials such as wood and hemp offer significant advantages, including low embodied energy and, in some cases, the potential for carbon sequestration [3], [4], [5].

The aim of this study is to compare the environmental performance of two single-family houses in south-eastern (SE) Europe. The first house consists of a conventional masonry of reinforced concrete and bricks, while the second house uses a timber construction and hemp-based insulation. The environmental impact of both houses was assessed using LCA methodology in line with EN 15978 [6], focusing on global warming potential (GWP). The results help to understand how the choice of materials affects carbon emissions and promote more sustainable building practices in the region.

2 Methodology

In this study, a comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) of two single-family houses is carried out in accordance with the EN 15978 standard [6] which provides a framework for the environmental assessment of buildings. The environmental performance assessment was based on standardized life cycle data and conducted in accordance with European frameworks for sustainable building analysis. Both houses are designed for similar functional performance in terms of housing capacity, thermal comfort, and service life. One house was built with conventional materials (mainly reinforced concrete and clay bricks), while the other was built with natural materials (a timber construction system with hemp-based insulation). Both houses are designed for a single household of four people and have similar gross internal floor areas. A description of the basic features and elements for both houses can be found in Table 1. The functional unit for this study is defined as 1 m²

f gross internal floor area of single-family house located in a moderate climate of SE Europe, over a service life of 50 years.

Table 1. Basic features and materials of the houses

Feature/Element	Conventional House	Alternative House
Basic Information		
Location	Bistra, Croatia	Mokri Potok, Slovenia
Gross Internal Floor Area (m ²)	144	117
Number of Floors	Ground floor + first floor	Ground floor + first floor
Number of Occupants	4	4
Reference Service Life (years)	50	50
Key Materials		
Foundations	Reinforced Concrete	Reinforced Concrete
Load Bearing Walls	Brick Wall	Wooden Frame Wall
Intermediate Floor Structure	Reinforced Concrete	Timber
Facade System	ETICS (Mineral Wool)	Hemp Insulation with Clay Plaster
Roof Structure	Reinforced Concrete/Timber	Timber
Roof Covering	Sheet Metal	Concrete Roof Tile
Plaster	Cement-Lime	Clay/NHL
Doors and Windows	PVC frame	Wooden frame

2.1 System boundaries

While comprehensive LCAs of buildings typically include the operational phase, accounting for energy and water use in modules B1-B3 and B6-B7, this study strategically limits itself to embodied carbon emissions stemming from building materials and their end-of-life management. This deliberate choice is underpinned by several important considerations that reflect the evolving landscape of sustainable building practices. The rationale behind this focused approach is to recognize the considerable body of existing research and regulatory frameworks that already address the environmental impacts of the operational energy of buildings [7]. These include building regulations, energy efficiency standards and the ongoing development and introduction of nearly zero energy buildings [8]. The life cycle phases considered in this study are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Building's LCA stages considered in this study [6]

2.2 Data sources and assumptions

The material quantities for both houses were derived from detailed bills of quantities and architectural plans. Data on the environmental impact of the building products used was taken from Environmental product declarations (EPDs). Where available, verified third-party EPDs were preferred to ensure the quality and specificity of the data. For materials for which no specific EPDs were available in the database, generic data sets were used, with careful consideration of regional relevance where possible. The assumptions regarding the transportation distances of the materials to the construction site were based on realistic regional averages. Assumptions for the end-of-life phase, including demolition methods and waste treatment scenarios, were also based on typical practices in SE Europe.

3 Results and discussion

This section presents the results of LCA carried out for conventional and alternative single-family houses. The analysis focuses on Global Warming Potential (GWP), a key indicator of environmental impact, and the results are presented in Table 33.

The total GWP for the conventional house is 102,547.49 kg CO₂e, while the alternative house has a significantly lower total GWP of 9,517.87 kg CO₂e. This considerable difference shows that the alternative house has a 90.7% lower embodied carbon footprint compared to the conventional house.

To get a more accurate and long-term perspective, it is important to consider the GWP in relation to the floor area of each house and its reference service life. The conventional house has a gross internal floor area of 144 m², while the alternative house has an area of 117 m², and both have a service life of 50 years. The GWP per square meter takes into account the difference in house size, while the GWP per square meter and year distributes the impact over the lifetime of the house and

illustrates the annual environmental impact per residential unit. Both figures clearly underline the environmental advantage of the alternative house (Table 2).

Table 2. GWP in relation to floor area and reference service life

GWP metric	Conventional House	Alternative House
GWP per square meter over service life of 50 years, kg CO ₂ e/m ²	712.14	81.35
GWP per square meter and year, kg CO ₂ e/m ² /year	14.24	1.63

For the conventional house, the largest contribution to the total GWP comes from the material production phase (A1-A3) with emissions of 58053.43 kg CO₂e. In contrast, the alternative house shows a different pattern. The material production phase (A1-A3) has a negative GWP value of -28088.44 kg CO₂e. This negative value indicates significant carbon sequestration in the materials used in the alternative house, especially wood and hemp insulation. Carbon sequestration means that the materials absorb more CO₂ from the atmosphere during their growth than they release during production, resulting in a positive environmental effect at this stage. However, the largest positive contribution to GWP for the alternative house comes from the waste processing phase (C3), specifically from the C3-biogenic subcategory, with emissions of 30187.59 kg CO₂e. Fig. 2 visually compares the GWP of each life cycle phase for the conventional and alternative house, highlighting the carbon sequestration (negative GWP) in the material production phase (A1-A3) of the alternative house.

Transportation to the site (A4) and the construction/installation process (A5) contribute relatively little to the overall GWP for both houses. The conventional house has 1883.22 kg CO₂e in the A4 phase and 6240.66 kg CO₂e in the A5 phase, while the alternative house has significantly lower values of 364.8 kg CO₂e and 779.61 kg CO₂e in the same phases. The differences in these phases result from the fact that the alternative house was largely built from locally sourced materials and therefore the transportation distances were shorter compared to the conventional house.

The material replacement and refurbishment phase (B4-B5) contributes only moderately to the overall GWP. The conventional house has 5557.8 kg CO₂e in this phase, while the alternative house has 2570.82 kg CO₂e. This indicates that the choice of materials influences the emissions associated with maintenance and renovation throughout the life of the building.

The end-of-life phase (C1-C4) has a significant impact on the overall GWP for both houses. As mentioned above, the alternative house has a higher GWP in this phase (33891.08 kg CO₂e) than the conventional house (30812.39 kg CO₂e), which is mainly due to the emissions from biogenic waste processing. Biogenic carbon is

considered temporarily stored during the use phase and released at the end of life. EoL results are based on EPDs, in which each material has defined waste treatment scenarios. Although the end-of-life phase (C1–C4) shows higher GWP values for the alternative house compared to the conventional one, this highlights the crucial importance of conducting sensitivity analyses for EoL scenarios, especially in buildings that use bio-based materials.

Table 3. Global warming potential for each house and life cycle stage

LCA stage		Global Warming Potential Total (kg CO ₂ e)	
		Conventional house	Alternative house
A1-A3	Construction Materials	58,053.43	-28,088.44
A4	Transportation to site	1,883.22	364.8
A5	Construction/installation process	6,240.66	779.61
B4-B5	Material replacement and refurbishment	5,557.8	2,570.82
C1	Deconstruction/demolition	788.07	548.02
C2	Waste transport	1,443.24	351.13
C3	Waste processing	1,975.25	444.09
C3-biogenic	Biogenic waste processing	23,744.64	30,187.59
C4	Waste disposal	37.85	23.83
C4-biogenic	Biogenic waste disposal	2,823.33	2,336.42
Total		102,547.49	9,517.87

Fig. 2. Visual Comparison of GWP by Life Cycle Stage

Table 4. provides a breakdown of the top 5 materials contributing to the fossil GWP within the material production stage (A1-A3) for both house designs. The fossil GWP refers to the global warming potential resulting from the combustion of fossil fuels used in material production.

For the conventional house, ready-mix concrete contributes by far the most to the fossil GWP with 44.2 t CO_{2e} or 61.4% of the total fossil GWP in the A1-A3 phase. Other important factors are the ETICS insulation system (3.9 t CO_{2e}, 5.7%), fibre-reinforced screed (3.6 t CO_{2e}, 5.2%), PVC framed windows (3.0 t CO_{2e}, 4.3%) and reinforcement steel (2.8 t CO_{2e}, 4.1%). These materials illustrate the dependence of conventional construction methods on energy-intensive materials.

For the alternative house, ready-mixed concrete also has the highest fossil GWP contribution within the A1-A3 level (4.5 t CO_{2e}, 69.3%), although the overall magnitude is much lower than for the conventional house. This indicates that although the alternative design reduces the use of concrete, it is still a significant factor. Other notable factors include concrete roof tiles (1.4 t CO_{2e}, 21.9%), wood fiberboard (1.4 t CO_{2e}, 21.6%), wood frame windows (0.98 t CO_{2e}, 15.1%) and timber (0.6 t CO_{2e}, 9.3%). It is important to note that even for the alternative house, concrete-based materials remain an important source of fossil fuel emissions.

Table 4. Top 5 materials contributing to fossil GWP in A1-A3

	Material	House Type	Fossil GWP (t CO _{2e})	% of A1- A3
1	Ready-mix Concrete	Conventional	44,20	61.4%
2	ETICS Insulation System	Conventional	3,90	5.7%
3	Fibre-Reinforced Screed	Conventional	3,60	5.2%
4	PVC Frame Windows	Conventional	3,00	4.3%
5	Reinforcement Steel (Rebar)	Conventional	2,80	4.1%
1	Ready-mix Concrete	Alternative	4,50	69.3%
2	Concrete Roof Tiles	Alternative	1,40	21.9%
3	Wood Fiberboards	Alternative	1,40	21.6%
4	Wooden Frame Windows	Alternative	0,98	15.1%
5	Timber	Alternative	0,60	9.3%

4 Conclusions

The comparative life cycle assessment of a conventional and an alternative single-family house in south-east Europe showed a significantly lower GWP for the alternative house design. The alternative house showed a 90.7% reduction in total

GWP compared to the conventional house, primarily due to the use of bio-based materials such as wood and hemp, which have significant carbon sequestration during material production (A1-A3). This carbon sequestration offsets a significant portion of the emissions generated in other phases of the life cycle. However, the analysis has also shown the importance of considering the end-of-life cycle. The waste processing phase (C3), particularly the processing of biogenic waste, was found to be the main contributor to GWP in the alternative house, highlighting the need for sustainable end-of-life management strategies for bio-based materials.

Normalizing the results by floor area and service life provides a more practical perspective, with the alternative house having a GWP of 81.35 kg CO₂e/m² and 1.63 kg CO₂e/m²/year, compared to 712.14 kg CO₂e/m² and 14.24 kg CO₂e/m²/year for the conventional house. These values underline the long-term environmental benefits of the alternative construction method based on a living space unit.

Based on the results given, it is necessary to develop more realistic and region-specific scenarios for EoL of bio-based materials. Incorporating scenario analysis and sensitivity assessments can significantly enhance the credibility of results.

Future research should focus on extending the scope of the LCA to the operational phase of buildings, including energy and water consumption, in order to provide a more comprehensive assessment. Investigating the economic feasibility and social acceptability of alternative house designs in the south-east European market would also be valuable to promote their adoption.

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